

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Diversity of leaf epidermal structures used in biosystematics of rice species

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The rice genus contains 24 annual or perennial species, including two cultivated rice species, i.e., the Asian rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) and African rice (*O. glaberrima* Steud), and 22 wild species in the tropics.

In this study, morphological features of the leaf epidermis of 22 rice species (see table) were observed by light microscopy to find characters for

identifying species and to assess systematic relationships in the genus. For example, *O. schlechteri*, *O. ridleyi*, *O. longiglumis*, *O. granulata*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. officinalis*, *O. minuta*, *O. sativa*, *O. nivara*, and *O. meyeriana* have elliptic stomatal complexes, whereas in other species they are rhombic. The size of papillae on most epidermal surfaces ranged from small (1.5-4.4 μm diam) to medium (9-18 μm) to large (21-30 μm), and their size and distribution were very useful in identifying species. In addition, the number and location of the small papillae in stomatal complexes differed between species.

Based on the following combinations of leaf epidermal characters, i.e., the size and distribution of papillae on the abaxial surface of the epidermis, the

number and location of the small papillae in stomatal complexes, and the shapes of stomatal complexes, the 22 studied *Oryza* species could be divided into three main groups.

In the first group, which included *O. longiglumis*, *O. ridleyi*, *O. meyeriana*, and *O. granulata*, neither large- nor medium-sized papillae (in some cases, extremely rare small papillae) were found on the surfaces of epidermis and no small papillae were found in stomatal complexes. All species in this group had elliptic stomatal complexes (Fig. 1). This group included species classified in *O. meyeriana* and *O. ridleyi* complexes based on external morphological characters.

The second group included *O. brachyantha*, diploid and tetraploid *O. officinalis*, *O. minuta*, *O. eichingeri*, *O. punctata*, *O. latifolia*, *O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, *O. rhizomatis*, and *O. australiensis*. In these species, usually no large papillae were observed, but medium-sized and densely populated small papillae were found to cover the surfaces of epidermis, and at least four small papillae were found in stomatal complexes (in guard cells) of most species. This group contains all species in the *O. officinalis* complex.

1. Abaxial leaf epidermis of *O. ridleyi* (x1120), showing no papillae on the surface of the epidermis, and elliptic stomatal complexes without papillae.

International Rice Genebank Collection (IRGC) number, chromosome number, genomic group, and distribution of rice species used in the experiment. Beijing, China.

Species	IRGC accession no.	Chromosome number $2n =$	Genome	Country of origin
<i>O. barthii</i> A. Chev.	103908	24	AA	Tanzania
<i>O. glumaepatula</i> Steud.	105465	24	AA	Guiana
<i>O. longistaminata</i> Chev. et Roehr.	101221	24	AA	Mali
<i>O. rneridionalis</i> Ng	101147	24	AA	Tropical Australia
<i>O. nivara</i> Sharma et Shastry	102163	24	AA	Taiwan
	100593			
<i>O. rufipogon</i> Griff.	105567	24	AA	Indonesia
<i>O. sativa</i> L.	36865	24	AA	China
<i>O. punctata</i> Kotechy ex Steud.	104975	24	BB	Kenya
<i>O. eichingeri</i> Peter	101424	24	CC	Uganda
	105182			Uganda
	105163			Uganda
<i>O. officinalis</i> Wall ex Watt	100176	24	CC	Thailand
	100957 (4x)	48 ^a		India
<i>O. rhizomatis</i> Vaughan	105448	24	CC	Sri Lanka
<i>O. minuta</i> J. S. Presl. et C. B. Presl.	103879	48	BBCC	Philippines
<i>O. alta</i> Swallen	101395	48	CCDD	Mexico
<i>O. grandiglumis</i> (Doell) Prod.	106241	48	CCDD	Brazil
<i>O. latifolia</i> Desv.	100962	48	CCDD	Guatemala
<i>O. australiensis</i> Domin.	10370	24	EE	Tropical Australia
<i>O. granulata</i> Nees et Arn ex Wall.	106468	24	GG	Lao PDR
<i>O. meyeriana</i> (Roll. et Mor. ex Steud.) Baill	104990	24	GG	Malaysia
<i>O. longiglumis</i> Jansen	105562	48	JJHH	Indonesia
<i>O. ridleyi</i> Hook f.	105973	48	JJHH	Indonesia
	100877			Thailand
<i>O. brachyantha</i> Chev. et Roehr.	105172	24	FF	Cameroon
<i>O. schlechteri</i> Pilger	PNG1 ^b	48	??	Papua New Guinea

^aThis tetraploid taxon was described as *Oryza malampuzhaensis* Krish. et Chand., but its morphological features are very similar to those of *O. officinalis*. Following the treatment of Vaughan (1989), it is included in *O. officinalis*. ^bField collection number.

2. Abaxial leaf epidermis of *O. nivara* (x1 120), showing small and medium-sized papillae on the surface of epidermis, and rhombic stomatal complexes with 6-8 small papillae in subsidiary cells (indicated by arrows).

The third group included *O. sativa*, *O. nivara*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. longistaminata*, *O. lumaepatula*, *O. meridionalis*, *O. barthii*, and *O. schlechteri*. The abaxial leaf epidermis of these species was usually covered with large, medium-sized, and small papillae. In addition, more than four (usually 6-8) small papillae were found in guard cells or subsidiary cells of the stomatal complexes (Fig. 2). Most species in the second and third groups had rhombic stomatal complexes. This group is correlated to the morphologic *O. sativa* complex, except for *O. schlechteri*, which does not belong to any of the morphologic complexes.

These results largely agree with previous biosystematic studies of rice species that apply other methodologies, i.e., species within complexes have rather close relationships whereas those between complexes have a comparatively distant relationship. These results also show that leaf epidermal characters provide additional information for species identification in *Oryza*. ■

Genetics

Heterosis for physicochemical characters in rice

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Reports on heterosis for the physicochemical grain quality characters in rice are limited. We studied the heterotic manifestations in nine grain quality characters in 30 hybrids involving six parents—IR50, ADT37, ADT41, Duansan, TKM6, and ADT39. The hybrids were created by full diallel mating of these six parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during the 1993-94 dry

season. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in three 3-m rows at 30- × 20-cm spacing. Observations were recorded for five randomly selected plants per replication.

Seeds were dehulled in a McGill sample sheller and milled in a Kett rice polisher. Cooking characters were measured as suggested by Juliano and Perez (1984). Amylose content was measured by the method of Juliano (1971), and the protein per grain was estimated by the method of Shenoy et al (1994).

The performance of hybrids over mid-parent (relative heterosis) and over the better parent (heterobeltiosis) was estimated following standard procedure (see table). The heterosis for

Summary of heterosis on nine physicochemical characters in hybrid rice.

Character	Relative heterosis		Heterobeltiosis		Top-ranking hybrids
	Range	Significant crosses ^a (no.)	Range	Significant crosses ^a (no.)	
Kernel length	-7.98 to 25.36	15	-18.60 to 19.65	8	ADT41/IR50 ADT39/ADT37 TKM6/ADT39 TKM6/ADT37
Kernel breadth	-40.63 to 18.06	15	-44.84 to 15.12	9	TKM6/ADT39 ADT41/IR50
Kernel L-B ratio	-12.68 to 68.27	10	-32.61 to 58.32	6	-
Kernel length after cooking	-21.34 to 26.43	14	-23.48 to 41.36	6	Duansan/ADT39 IR50/ADT37 ADT41/IR50
Kernel breadth after cooking	-9.26 to 31.89	14	-31.79 to 30.64	15	Duansan/ADT39 Duansan/IR50 ADT41/IR50
Linear elongation	-27.38 to 41.69	12	-37.79 to 33.82	11	ADT39/ADT41 IR50/Duansan ADT41/IR50
Elongation index	-55.84 to 59.74	13	-55.84 to 59.74	9	Duansan/ADT39 Duansan/ADT41 ADT41/IR50
Amylose (%)	-44.71 to 56.62	22	-44.78 to 42.60	19	ADT39/ADT37 TKM6/Duansan
Protein grain ⁻¹	-29.03 to 41.59	12	-42.11 to 32.69	7	ADT37/IR50 ADT39/Duansan ADT41/IR50

^aSignificant in the desirable direction.